

Conference Abstract

The challenges we've overcome and the new opportunities for using environmental DNA in biomonitoring aquatic resources

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Abstract

Since the first kick-off meeting of the DNAqua-Net until now, the interest and use of environmental DNA in scientific studies, management and even the start of companies has exponentially grown. It is often said that this is *how we will* monitor biodiversity in the future. Together, with over 400 members from 39 countries making up the COST Action, we have honed our DNA detection methods, determined the many trade-offs, identified and filled gaps in our knowledge, and made steps towards standardization. In my seminar, I will highlight some of the major challenges we've overcome and propose the opportunities and research directions I see for the future of using eDNA in biodiversity monitoring. We are poised at the start of the UN's Decade on Ecosystem Restoration and there is no better time to cease DNA-based monitoring technology for making the best informed decisions for the future of life on our planet.

Keywords

eDNA, biodiversity, monitoring, DNAqua-Net

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